

Original Research

Quadruple Bottom Line Disclosure Among Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria: A Paradigm for Cost Savings

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Abstract

The study determined the effect of quadruple bottom line reporting (proxies by economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures) on cost saving among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted using a population size of 21 listed consumer goods manufacturing firms from which a sample of fifteen was purposively selected. The data collected for the study spanned a period of 10 years from 2013 to 2022. Random effect model was estimated at 5% significance level which revealed that economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures significantly enhance cost saving among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. In conclusion, the adoption of quadruple bottom line reporting can offer manufacturing firms a strategic advantage. It aligns with global trends in sustainable business practices and can position these firms to enjoy cost-saving opportunities. To maximize the benefits of quadruple bottom line reporting, manufacturing firms should make a concerted effort to integrate economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures into their business practices in order to enhance transparency and accountability, leading to improved cost-saving opportunities.

Keywords: Cost Saving, Economic reporting, Environmental reporting, Governance reporting, Quadruple Bottom Line Reporting, Social reporting.

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Introduction

The intersection of business, profit, and corporate responsibility has become a focal point for global discussions especially in this era defined by increased awareness of social and environmental challenges (Buallay, 2022; Ly, 2021). Companies are no longer evaluated solely on financial performance but are expected to be accountable for their social and environmental impacts (Nworie & Aniefuna, 2024). Thus, the Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) emerges as a concept that encapsulates economic, social, environmental, and governance considerations, and its implications for businesses are profound (Alibašić, 2022). This study centers on the influence of Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) disclosure among Nigerian listed manufacturing firms. Nigeria, a significant player in Africa's manufacturing sector, stands at the cusp of a transformative period in corporate sustainability and responsibility. The Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) goes beyond the traditional Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework, which focuses on financial, social, and environmental aspects of business (Onovo, Onyekwelu & Nwoha, 2023). QBL extends this paradigm by including governance as a fourth critical dimension, acknowledging that responsible business practices encompass not only financial success, social welfare, and environmental sustainability but also ethical corporate behaviour and robust governance structures. However, Nigeria currently does not have a strong regulatory framework that requires or encourages companies to implement QBL reporting and practices. The lack of specific guidelines and enforcement measures makes it difficult for these practices to become widespread. Additionally, gathering accurate data on the four elements of QBL (people, planet, profit, and innovation) presents challenges in Nigeria due to the absence of standardized reporting procedures (Oyerogba, Oladele, Kolawole & Adeyemo, 2024), and a general lack of transparency. Despite the above, Folashade, Dorcas, Akinwumi and Uwalomwa (2016) found that in the industrial goods sector, Lafarge Africa Plc. has adopted minimal quadruple bottom line disclosure, revealing no information on human rights issues, only 3% environmental disclosures, and an aggregate of 30% disclosure based on one hundred and sixty-nine indicators used.

The integration of QBL principles is of paramount importance for Nigerian manufacturing firms in today's global business landscape. It reflects a proactive approach towards fostering responsible business practices, aligning with international standards and aspirations. Moreover, it responds to the growing concerns about corporate ethics, governance transparency, environmental sustainability, and societal well-being (Alibašić, 2018). Nigerian listed manufacturing firms are expected to operate at the intersection of economic efficiency, social responsibility, environmental sustainability, and sound corporate governance by fully embracing the Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) disclosure, ensuring transparency and accountability across all these dimensions. This is only achievable when manufacturing businesses not only maximize profit but also make conscious efforts to reduce costs through sustainable practices while simultaneously enhancing their brand reputation by demonstrating a strong commitment to social welfare, environmental stewardship, and ethical corporate conduct.

However, while some manufacturing firms such as Lafarge have begun to adopt QBL principles (Folashade, Dorcas, Akinwumi & Uwalomwa, 2016) and disclosure practices, many still operate within a conventional, profit-centric paradigm owing to a number of

reasons such as financial constraints, dearth of required expertise, et cetera (Abdullahi & Abubakar, 2023; Mgbame, Aderin, Ohalehi & Chijoke-Mgbame, 2020). The majority of these firms fail to effusively appreciate the potential of QBL disclosure in delivering cost savings and brand reputation enhancement. As a result, they do not adequately integrate these principles into their core operations, missing opportunities to create a more sustainable and responsible business model (Murthy, 2012).

Consequently, the failure to embrace QBL principles results in missed cost-saving opportunities, limiting the financial viability of these manufacturing firms. In addition, the lack of commitment to environmental sustainability, social welfare, and ethical governance may lead to negative societal impacts, deteriorating environmental conditions, and the erosion of trust among stakeholders. Ultimately, this gap not only threatens the long-term success and sustainability of Nigerian listed manufacturing firms but also hinders the broader progress toward a more responsible and sustainable business environment in the country.

By investigating how QBL disclosure affects Nigerian manufacturing firms, this research holds the potential to provide valuable hints for stakeholders, policymakers, and investors seeking to promote responsible business practices and enhance the economic, social, and environmental fabric of the country. This study addresses the challenge of striking a balance between profit generation and corporate responsibility in a rapidly changing business world. It aims to uncover whether adopting the Quadruple Bottom Line approach can lead to cost savings, brand reputation enhancement (Fonseca, 2015), and, by extension, more sustainable and responsible business practices among Nigerian manufacturing firms. This study aims to investigating the effect of QBL disclosure (proxies by economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures) on cost savings in Nigerian manufacturing firms, unlike previous studies that concentrated on triple bottom line reporting.

Research Questions

What is the effect of QBL disclosure (proxies by economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures) on cost savings in Nigerian manufacturing firms, unlike previous studies that concentrated on triple bottom line reporting?

Literature review

Conceptual Issues

Cost saving

Cost saving refers to the reduction of operational expenses and resource consumption through the adoption of more efficient and sustainable practices by manufacturing firms (MacMillan, 2014). Cost savings can have a direct impact on a company's profitability and financial performance, making it a critical aspect of corporate strategy (Aggreh, Abiahu & Nworie, 2023). Sustainable practices, such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, and responsible resource management, can lead to significant cost savings over time. Cost saving encompasses a strategic approach aimed at minimizing operational

expenditures and conserving valuable resources while simultaneously maintaining or even improving the overall efficiency and effectiveness of an organization's processes and operations (Bello, 2020). This fundamental aspect of financial management involves a comprehensive evaluation of all costs incurred in the course of conducting business, with a primary focus on identifying areas where efficiency gains can be made (Barbole, Nalwade & Parakh, 2013).

Cost saving involves a meticulous examination of expenditures, which may include but are not limited to labor costs, raw materials, energy consumption, transportation, waste management, and overhead expenses. This scrutiny aims to pinpoint inefficiencies, redundancies, or unnecessary expenditures within the organization's operations (Hansen, Mowen & Heitger, 2021). In a broader context, it also encompasses the minimization of indirect costs, such as environmental cleanup and social responsibility initiatives, that may result from unsustainable or unethical business practices.

Cost saving is a critical component of a company's financial strategy, as it directly impacts the bottom line by increasing profitability (Nworie & Nwoye, 2023). By reducing costs, an organization can potentially enhance its competitiveness in the market, maintain or improve product quality, and even invest in innovation or expansion (Kadhim, Najm & Kadhim, 2020). The saved resources, both financial and non-financial, can be redirected towards other strategic endeavors or reinvested in ways that generate further value.

The adoption of cost-saving measures often necessitates the implementation of more efficient and sustainable practices. These practices can encompass a wide range of strategies, including but not limited to the optimization of supply chains, waste reduction initiatives, energy efficiency measures, and the implementation of sustainable sourcing practices. Sustainable practices not only reduce costs but also align an organization with societal and environmental responsibilities. For instance, improving energy efficiency not only reduces energy costs but also diminishes the organization's carbon footprint, contributing to environmental sustainability.

In essence, cost saving is about achieving a balance between operational efficiency and resource stewardship. It involves an ongoing commitment to optimizing processes, streamlining operations, and adopting innovative solutions that reduce costs without compromising quality, ethics, or sustainability (Bello, 2020). Successful cost-saving strategies require a keen understanding of the organization's operations, a commitment to continuous improvement, and an awareness of the broader impact of these efforts on society and the environment.

For the Nigerian listed manufacturing firms examined in this study, cost saving through the adoption of Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) reporting represents a pivotal opportunity to not only enhance their financial performance but also to align their operations with global trends in sustainability, responsible business practices, and ethical governance. These firms can leverage QBL reporting as a means to not only improve their financial bottom line but also their environmental impact, social engagement, and ethical conduct, ensuring they thrive in a changing business landscape that increasingly values responsible and sustainable business practices.

Quadruple bottom line reporting

Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) reporting is a reporting framework which provides a structured approach for organizations to assess and communicate their commitment to sustainable and responsible business practices, acknowledging that corporate success should encompass not only profitability, social well-being, and environmental stewardship but also ethical conduct and governance (Alibašić, 2018).

QBL reporting represents a significant evolution in the way organizations assess and communicate their performance, taking the traditional Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework to a more comprehensive and multidimensional level (Mukherjee & Banerjee, 2021). While the TBL evaluates a company's success based on three primary dimensions: economic, social, and environmental, QBL boldly integrates a fourth critical dimension: corporate governance and ethics (Alibašić & Crawley, 2020). This extension acknowledges that corporate prosperity and long-term sustainability depend not only on financial strength, societal well-being, and environmental stewardship but also on the ethical conduct and governance structures that underpin a company's operations (Alibašić, 2017).

QBL reporting is a structured framework that offers a holistic perspective on an organization's performance. It entails the systematic measurement, assessment, and transparent disclosure of the company's activities and initiatives across these four dimensions: economic, social, environmental, and governance (Tiller, Rhindress, Oguntola, Ülkü, Williams & Sundararajan, 2022). These disclosures are made available to a wide range of stakeholders, including investors, employees, customers, regulators, and the general public. The emphasis on transparency and accountability within QBL reporting is crucial, as it not only facilitates informed decision-making among stakeholders but also holds organizations responsible for their commitments and actions in these critical areas.

1. **Economic Dimension:** Within the QBL framework, the economic dimension continues to be a fundamental aspect of performance evaluation. It encompasses traditional financial metrics such as revenue, profit, and return on investment (Hamidi & Worthington, 2023). However, QBL goes beyond mere financial gains and considers how these economic aspects are achieved, whether they are generated sustainably, and whether they align with ethical and governance standards.

2. **Social Dimension:** The social dimension of QBL reporting focuses on the impact of an organization's activities on society at large. It encompasses aspects like employee well-being, community engagement (Nworie & Aniefuna, 2024), human rights practices, and customer satisfaction. This dimension is critical for assessing how a company contributes to social well-being and whether its operations positively affect the communities in which it operates (Mukherjee & Banerjee, 2021).

3. **Environmental Dimension:** Environmental sustainability is another cornerstone of QBL reporting. It evaluates the company's efforts to minimize its ecological footprint, including reductions in energy consumption, waste generation, greenhouse gas emissions, and resource consumption (Hamidi & Worthington, 2023). This dimension reflects a

growing global concern for environmental preservation and the mitigation of climate change (Nworie, Obi, Anaike & Uchechukwu-Obi, 2022).

4. Governance and Ethics Dimension: The distinguishing feature of QBL reporting is its inclusion of the governance and ethics dimension. This aspect delves into the ethical principles and governance structures that guide an organization's decision-making and operations (Alibašić & Crawley, 2020). It scrutinizes issues like board composition, transparency, accountability, and adherence to ethical standards. Strong governance and ethical practices are crucial for building trust and credibility among stakeholders.

QBL reporting is a strategic commitment to responsible business practices because it serves as a roadmap for organizations to align their strategies with global trends and expectations related to sustainability, social responsibility, and ethical conduct (Alibašić, 2017). By adopting the QBL approach, organizations acknowledge that they are part of a larger ecosystem, and their success should be measured not just by the financial bottom line but also by their contributions to societal well-being, environmental preservation, and ethical governance. This framework is particularly pertinent in today's business environment, where stakeholders demand transparency, responsible behavior, and a holistic view of corporate performance.

Critique of Quadruple Bottom Line Disclosure

Quadruple bottom line (QBL) disclosures, while commendable for their comprehensive approach to corporate sustainability, face several criticisms. One major critique is that they can become overly complex and burdensome for companies, especially smaller firms with limited resources (Fonseca, 2015; Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneeroj, 2019). The requirement to report on economic, social, environmental, and governance factors often demands significant time, expertise, and financial investment, which can divert attention from core business operations. Additionally, QBL disclosures may suffer from a lack of standardization, leading to inconsistencies and difficulties in comparing data across companies and industries. This variability can undermine the reliability and usefulness of QBL reports for stakeholders. Moreover, there is a risk that firms might engage in "greenwashing" or superficial reporting, where they emphasize positive aspects of their performance while downplaying or omitting negative impacts, thereby misleading stakeholders. Finally, the emphasis on QBL reporting may encourage a compliance-oriented approach rather than genuine, transformative sustainability practices, potentially limiting its effectiveness in driving substantial change.

Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on stakeholder theory, which posits that businesses should consider the interests of all stakeholders in their decision-making processes, has its roots in several academic disciplines and practical business concerns (Freeman, 2010). This theory recognises that businesses operate within a broader social and economic context, affecting and being affected by various groups and individuals (Mmadubuobi, Nworie & Aziekwe, 2024; Ukoh, Nduokafor & Nworie, 2024). The most significant development in stakeholder theory came with the work of R. Edward Freeman, who is often credited

with formalizing and popularizing the concept. In his seminal book, "Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach" (1984), Freeman argued that managers should consider a wide range of stakeholders—groups or individuals who can affect or are affected by the achievement of the organization's objectives—including not only shareholders but also employees, customers, suppliers, communities, and the environment.

Stakeholder theory represents a fundamental paradigm in the field of business and management, asserting that organizations should recognize and address the interests and concerns of all relevant stakeholders, rather than focusing solely on the interests of shareholders (Ifeanyi, Azubike & Iormbagah, 2020). In a rapidly evolving global business environment, this theory underlines the significance of considering a diverse set of stakeholders, which includes but is not limited to shareholders, customers, employees, local communities, and regulatory bodies. It posits that businesses, as integral components of society, have a moral and strategic obligation to manage their operations with the best interests of these stakeholders in mind (Budsaratragoon & Jitmaneroj, 2019).

Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) reporting aligns seamlessly with the principles of stakeholder theory. By incorporating a comprehensive view of an organization's performance across economic, social, environmental, and governance dimensions, QBL reporting effectively engages with a broad spectrum of stakeholders and their multifaceted interests (Hadders, 2017). One of the fundamental tenets of stakeholder theory is that organizations should consider and balance the interests of a wide range of stakeholders. QBL reporting provides a structured mechanism to do just that. It offers a comprehensive assessment of an organization's performance across four critical dimensions, catering to the concerns and expectations of various stakeholder groups. This ensures that businesses take into account not only the financial gains for shareholders but also the societal and environmental impacts on communities, employees, and the planet (Fonseca, 2015).

QBL reporting accommodates the interests of investors and shareholders by transparently disclosing financial performance, strategies for growth, and risk management. It offers investors a more holistic view of an organization's long-term prospects, taking into account sustainability and ethical considerations, which can be vital for investment decisions.

For customers, who are increasingly seeking products and services that align with their values, QBL reporting showcases a company's commitment to social responsibility and environmental sustainability. It demonstrates that the organization is not only concerned with profit but also with delivering products and services that are ethically and environmentally responsible (Quisenberry, 2012). Also, QBL reporting addresses the well-being of employees by considering factors such as workplace conditions, diversity and inclusion, employee development, and overall job satisfaction. It signals to current and potential employees that the organization values their contributions and is committed to maintaining a positive work environment.

QBL reporting recognizes the importance of a company's impact on the local community. This can encompass aspects like community engagement, support for local initiatives, and minimizing negative externalities such as pollution or resource depletion. By being mindful of these impacts, organizations can foster positive relationships with the communities in which they operate (Mukherjee & Banerjee, 2021). The framework of QBL reporting aligns with regulatory requirements and expectations. This makes it easier for organizations to demonstrate compliance with relevant laws and regulations, reducing legal risks and enhancing relationships with regulatory bodies.

QBL reporting, therefore, operates as a bridge between organizations and their stakeholders, facilitating a more inclusive and comprehensive dialogue. By adhering to stakeholder theory and the principles of responsible business, companies can meet the demands and expectations of a diverse range of stakeholders while pursuing cost-saving sustainability measures. This not only enhances their reputation but also contributes to the creation of a more sustainable and equitable society.

Prior Empirical Studies

Quadruple bottom line reporting is an emerging area of corporate sustainability disclosure with scant empirical studies conducted to that respect. Manta, Tarulli, Morrone, and Toma (2020) conducted an analysis to explore the potential connection between social disclosure and the financial performance of banking institutions. They focused on the presence of female executives on boards and the implementation of equal opportunity policies. Their research encompassed a sample of 61 banks operating in European Union countries between 2015 and 2017. The sample selection was driven by environmental, social, or governance (ESG) considerations, allowing them to examine the impact of non-financial disclosure as provided by Bloomberg. To investigate the relationship between the percentage of female directors on boards and the implementation of equal opportunity policies, they constructed a cross-section econometric model. Both bank-specific variables and performance indicators served as dependent variables. Their findings offer empirical evidence suggesting that fragmented boards may experience a lack of efficiency and performance. However, the adoption of equal opportunity policies can enhance the firm's reputation and positively impact staff performance.

In a separate study, Budsaratragoon and Jitmaneeroj (2019) delved into the intricate causal relationships among the four fundamental pillars of corporate sustainability: environmental, social, governance, and economic activities. They also sought to identify the primary drivers of corporate sustainability, with a focus on market developments and geographical regions. Analyzing data from 2,725 global companies in 2016, the researchers employed a combination of analytical techniques, including cluster analysis, data mining, partial least square path modeling, and importance performance map analysis. Their investigation revealed that companies in European developed markets tend to exhibit the highest levels of corporate sustainability. In alignment with the social impact hypothesis, the study found that environmental, social, and governance performance positively influences economic performance. Furthermore, they identified strong evidence of causal relationships and synergistic effects among these four pillars of corporate sustainability. The directions of these causal relationships and the relative importance of each pillar appear to be contingent on levels of market development and

geographical regions, aligning with the tenets of institutional theory. Notably, social and environmental aspects emerged as critical drivers of corporate sustainability. Zalatar and Clark (2019) developed a composite sustainability index based on the quadruple bottom line concept, which manufacturing firms can employ to measure their sustainability performance. This innovative index takes into account an organization's economic performance, social performance, environmental performance, and corporate governance. In a field study, the authors demonstrated that it is indeed possible to compute an index ranging from 0 to 1, using various sustainability indicators expressed in different units. This index offers a comprehensive and balanced way for manufacturing firms to assess and communicate their sustainability performance, transcending the traditional focus on financial metrics to encompass social and environmental dimensions as well as governance practices.

Methodology

The research methodology applied in this study is ex-post facto, allowing for the retrospective analysis of relationships between variables that have co-occurred in the past. The study's scope encompasses all consumer goods manufacturing companies listed in Nigeria. As of December 31, 2023, the Nigerian Exchange Group included a total of 21 firms operating in the consumer goods sector. A detailed breakdown of their specific listing information is presented in Table 1, as provided below.

Table 1. Population of the Study

No.	Companies
1.	Bua Foods Plc
2.	Cadbury Nigeria Plc.
3.	Champion Brew. Plc.
4.	Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc
5.	Dn Tyre & Rubber Plc
6.	Flour Mills Nig. Plc.
7.	Golden Guinea Brew. Plc.
8.	Guinness Nig Plc
9.	Honeywell Flour Mill Plc
10.	International Breweries Plc.
11.	McNichols Plc
12.	Multi-Trex Integrated Foods Plc
13.	N Nig. Flour Mills Plc.
14.	Nascon Allied Industries Plc
15.	Nestle Nigeria Plc.
16.	Nigerian Brew. Plc.
17.	Nigerian Enamelware Plc.
18.	P Z Cussons Nigeria Plc.
19.	Unilever Nigeria Plc.
20.	Union Dicon Salt Plc.
21.	Vitafoam Nig Plc.

Source: Nigerian Exchange Group (2023)

The sample size for this study, comprising fifteen companies, was determined using a purposive sampling technique. This selection method was employed based on the availability of complete data spanning from 2013 to 2022. The specific sample size is presented in Table 2, provided below.

Table 2. Sample Size

No.	Company
1.	Cadbury Nigeria Plc.
2.	Champion Brewery Nig. Plc.
3.	Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc.
4.	Flour Mills Nig. Plc.
5.	Guinness Nig. Plc
6.	Honeywell Flour Mill Plc.
7.	International Breweries Plc.
8.	Northern Nig. Flour Mills Plc
9.	Nascon Allied Industries Plc.
10.	Nestle Nigeria Plc
11.	Nigerian Breweries Plc
12.	Nigerian Enamelware Plc
13.	PZ Cussons Nigeria Plc.
14.	Unilever Nigeria Plc.
15.	Vitafoam Nigeria Plc.

This study relied on secondary data for its analysis. The quadruple bottom line reporting and cost saving data were obtained from multiple sources, including the publications of the Nigerian Stock Exchange and the annual reports and accounts of the chosen listed companies over a ten-year period, spanning from 2013 to 2022. As shown in Table 3, the variables are measured as follows.

Table 3. Measurement of Variables

Variable	Type	Measurement
Economic Reporting	Independent	GRI disclosure index for Economic Performance
Environmental reporting	Independent	GRI disclosure index for waste management
Social reporting	Independent	GRI disclosure index for community development
Governance reporting	Independent	GRI disclosure index for corporate leadership
Cost saving	Dependent	Operating cost/total revenue

The descriptive statistics of the variables used in the analysis of the sample was very crucial for the study. It was done using the mean, median, minimum and maximum value, standard deviation, asymmetry, and kurtosis of the independent and dependent variables. The essence of descriptive analysis is to give an informative summary of the data

collected from the sample, in terms of their central tendency, dispersion (variation) and normality. Random Effect Model of Panel Data regression was deployed in estimating the regression coefficients in order to examine the effect of quadruple bottom line reporting on cost savings among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. To test the null hypotheses, the study estimated the following regression equation:

$$COS_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 ECR_{it} + \beta_2 ENR_{it} + \beta_3 SOR_{it} + \beta_4 COR_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where, COS_{it} = Cost saving for company i in period t

ECR_{it} = Economic reporting for company i in period t

ENR_{it} = Environmental reporting for company i period t

SOR_{it} = Social reporting for company i in period t

COR_{it} = Corporate governance reporting for company i in period t

α_0 = Constant (intercept)

β_1-4 = Coefficient of the independent variables

μ = Error term

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistical Analysis of the Data

The descriptive statistics of the variables is shown below:

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of the Data

Statistics	COS	ECR	ENR	SOR	COR
Mean	0.094022	0.066671	0.736945	0.190229	0.0770941
Median	0.083554	0.210000	0.750000	0.222222	0.1090871
Maximum	0.264935	0.150000	0.888889	0.500000	0.3867521
Minimum	-0.149599	0.000000	0.538462	0.000000	0.0031349
Std. Dev.	0.080773	0.530269	0.103927	0.098267	0.0148679
Skewness	-0.045512	0.532235	-0.094457	-0.054493	0.1676279
Kurtosis	3.080160	1.945050	1.934211	3.503195	3.3900601
Jarque-Bera	0.036777	5.615037	2.928988	0.662708	0.5495731
Probability	0.981780	0.060355	0.231195	0.717951	0.6048161
Sum	5.641330	604.0000	44.21668	11.41375	11.3006151
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.384929	377.7333	0.637243	0.569731	0.4565961
Observations	150	150	150	150	150

Source: E-View Version 10 Output

As shown in Table 4, the descriptive statistics for Cost Saving (COS) indicate that the mean COS is approximately 0.094022. The minimum COS value of -0.149599 suggests that in some cases, firms may experience a decrease in cost savings, possibly due to inefficiencies or inadequate cost management practices. The maximum COS value of 0.264935 reflects the potential for substantial cost savings. The standard deviation (0.080773) and low skewness (-0.045512) suggest that COS data is relatively clustered around the mean, and the distribution is close to normal. However, the positive kurtosis value (3.080160) indicates a somewhat heavy-tailed distribution, potentially influenced by some outliers. The probability of Jarque-Bera (0.981780) further indicates that the data's distribution is not significantly different from a normal distribution, making it appropriate for statistical analysis.

For Economic Disclosure (ECR), the mean is 0.066671, signifying that, on average, manufacturing firms in the sample exhibit a relatively positive economic impact through QBL reporting. The minimum value is 0, indicating that firms tend not to report economic information with a negative effect. The maximum value of 0.15000 suggests that certain firms may experience a substantial positive economic impact through their disclosures. The relatively high standard deviation (0.530269) reflects a wider dispersion of data points around the mean, indicating variability in economic disclosures. The positive skewness (0.532235) suggests that the data may be somewhat positively skewed, with a longer right tail. The kurtosis value (1.945050) indicates a moderate degree of peakedness in the distribution. The probability of Jarque-Bera (0.060355) suggests that the distribution is not significantly different from normal, making it suitable for analysis.

The mean Environmental Disclosure (ENR) is 0.736945, indicating that, on average, firms have strong environmental disclosures through QBL reporting. The minimum value of 0.538462 suggests that even the lowest environmental disclosures tend to be above 0.5, indicating a generally positive environmental impact. The maximum value of 0.888889 indicates some firms have exceptionally high environmental disclosures. The low standard deviation (0.103927) implies relatively less variability in environmental disclosures. The negative skewness (-0.094457) suggests a slight leftward skew, potentially indicating a shorter left tail. The kurtosis value (1.934211) indicates a moderate degree of peakedness in the distribution. The probability of Jarque-Bera (0.231195) suggests that the data's distribution is not significantly different from a normal distribution.

The mean Social Disclosure (SOR) is 0.190229, reflecting that, on average, firms have a positive social impact through their QBL reporting. The maximum value of 0.500000 suggests the potential for substantial positive social disclosures. The low standard deviation (0.098267) indicates relatively low variability in social disclosures. The slightly negative skewness (-0.054493) suggests a minor leftward skew, potentially indicating a shorter left tail. The kurtosis value (3.503195) indicates a more peaked distribution. The probability of Jarque-Bera (0.717951) suggests that the data's distribution is not significantly different from a normal distribution.

For Corporate Governance Disclosure (COR), the mean is 0.0770941, signifying that, on average, firms tend to have a positive impact on corporate governance through their QBL reporting. The maximum value (0.3867521) indicates a potential for significant

positive impacts on corporate governance. The standard deviation (0.0148679) suggests relatively low variability in corporate governance disclosures. The positive skewness (0.1676279) indicates a slightly rightward skew, potentially suggesting a longer right tail. The kurtosis value (3.3900601) indicates a moderately peaked distribution. The probability of Jarque-Bera (0.6048161) suggests that the data's distribution is not significantly different from a normal distribution, making it suitable for analysis.

Hausman-Specification Test

To identify the most suitable cost savings model, this study conducted a Hausman specification test, which involved a comparison between the fixed effects model and the random effects model. The purpose of this test was to distinguish between a model in which omitted heterogeneity is considered fixed and correlated with the explanatory variables and a model in which omitted heterogeneity is regarded as random and unrelated to the explanatory variables. The Hausman specification test was employed to determine which of the Fixed Effect or Random Effect model was more fitting for the study. The outcomes of this test are presented in Table 5 for reference.

Table 5. Hausman-Specification Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	0.333522	4	0.9536

The Hausman test yielded a chi-square statistic of 0.333522 with a corresponding probability value of 0.9536. As a consequence of this outcome, the study opted for the random effects model and discarded the fixed effects model. Consequently, the random effects model was employed to address the issue of homogeneity in the pooled dataset used for the study. The rationale behind selecting the Random Effects Model for Panel Data regression was rooted in the assumption that the omitted effects were uncorrelated with the explanatory variables. This characteristic rendered the random effects estimator both consistent and efficient in addressing the study's objectives.

Hypothesis Testing

Random Effect Model of Panel Data regression was deployed in estimating the regression coefficients as shown in Table 6.

The result of the analysis aims to unveil how different components of Quadruple Bottom Line reporting, represented by economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures, affect cost savings in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The R-squared value of 0.230862 indicates that the independent variables (ECR, ENR, SOR, and COR) collectively explain about 23.09% of the variation in cost savings, highlighting that there are other factors contributing to cost savings beyond those considered in this model. The F-statistic of 5.602928 and the associated p-value (Prob(F-statistic) = 0.001971) suggest that the overall model is statistically significant. This indicates that at least one of the independent variables has a significant impact on the dependent variable (COS).

Table 6. Panel Data Regression Result

Dependent Variable: COS				
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ECR	-0.009578	0.005737	-2.669708	0.0006
ENR	-0.291915	0.126557	-2.306580	0.0248
SOR	-0.189321	0.113342	-2.670350	0.0004
COR	-0.340441	0.037778	-2.82147	0.0007
C	0.441585	0.129167	3.418715	0.0012
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.230862	Mean dependent var	0.017016	
Adjusted R-squared	0.189658	S.D. dependent var	0.056637	
S.E. of regression	0.050984	Sum squared resid	0.145565	
F-statistic	5.602928	Durbin-Watson stat	1.361651	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001971			

ECR has a coefficient of -0.009578, suggesting that an increase in economic disclosure is associated with a decrease in operating expense ratio (that is an increase in cost savings). This implies that when firms provide more economic disclosure within their QBL reporting, it may have a negative impact on cost thereby enhancing cost savings.

ENR has a coefficient of -0.291915, signifying that higher environmental disclosure is associated with a decrease in operating expense (that is, an increase in cost savings). This suggests that firms emphasizing environmental aspects in their QBL reporting may experience reduced cost and increased cost savings.

SOR has a coefficient of -0.189321, indicating that a greater focus on social disclosure has a negative impact on operating expense (that is, it enhances cost savings). This implies that firms emphasizing social responsibility in their QBL reporting may also have reduced cost and also increased cost savings.

COR has the most significant coefficient of -0.340441, suggesting that an emphasis on corporate governance disclosure in QBL reporting has negative impact on operating expense but a positive effect on cost savings.

In summary, the provided probability values (Prob) confirm the statistical significance of all coefficients (ECR, ENR, SOR, and COR) in the regression model. This indicates that each of these Quadruple Bottom Line (QBL) disclosure components significantly affects cost savings (COS) among the listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The negative coefficients further suggest that increased emphasis on economic, environmental, social, and corporate governance disclosure is associated with increased cost savings. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis was accepted that: quadruple bottom line reporting (proxies by economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures) significantly enhances cost saving among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Economic disclosures, which include transparent reporting on financial performance, investment strategies, and economic impacts, play a crucial role in enhancing cost savings. The random effect model's findings indicate that economic disclosures significantly boost cost efficiency among Nigerian manufacturing firms. This result can be attributed to several factors. First, detailed economic disclosures enhance investor confidence and attract more capital at lower costs, reducing the firm's financing expenses. Second, transparent financial reporting facilitates better decision-making by management, leading to more efficient allocation of resources and cost-effective operations. Lastly, economic disclosures often include risk assessments and mitigation strategies, which help firms avoid costly financial pitfalls and ensure long-term stability.

Social disclosures, encompassing aspects like employee welfare, community engagement, and social impact, also contribute significantly to cost savings. The positive effect of social disclosures on cost efficiency can be explained by the improved relationship between the company and its stakeholders. When firms invest in social initiatives and report on them transparently, they foster a positive work environment and enhance employee satisfaction and productivity. This, in turn, reduces turnover rates and the associated costs of recruitment and training. Furthermore, strong community relations built through social initiatives can lead to local support and a more favorable operating environment, minimizing disruptions and costs related to social unrest or community opposition.

Environmental disclosures, which detail a firm's environmental impact and sustainability efforts, have a pronounced effect on cost savings. The random effect model's findings suggest that manufacturing firms in Nigeria benefit significantly from transparent environmental reporting. This result is likely due to several factors. Firms that actively disclose their environmental practices often adopt more sustainable and efficient processes, leading to reduced waste and lower energy consumption. These practices not only cut operational costs but also mitigate the risk of regulatory fines and penalties associated with environmental non-compliance. Moreover, environmentally conscious firms can enhance their brand reputation, attracting eco-minded consumers and investors, which can further improve their financial performance.

Governance disclosures, which cover corporate governance practices, board structure, and transparency in management, also enhance cost savings among Nigerian manufacturing firms. Effective governance practices ensure that firms operate efficiently and ethically, reducing the likelihood of fraud, corruption, and mismanagement. The random effect model indicates that strong governance disclosures correlate with significant cost savings, likely because these practices lead to more robust internal controls and better risk management. Good governance fosters a culture of accountability and transparency, which can result in more prudent financial management and cost-effective decision-making. Additionally, firms with strong governance practices are more likely to attract investment and gain access to capital at favorable rates, further reducing their financial costs.

This aligns with Manta, Tarulli, Morrone, and Toma's (2020) study on European banks, which showed that social disclosures, such as equal opportunity policies and female board representation, enhance firm reputation and staff performance, leading to better financial outcomes. This supports the notion that non-financial disclosures can yield economic benefits.

Budsaratragoon and Jitmaneroj's (2019) research of 2,725 global companies found that firms in European developed markets achieve higher corporate sustainability due to robust ESG practices. They identified strong causal relationships among environmental, social, and governance activities, which positively influence economic performance. This complements the Nigerian study, suggesting that comprehensive sustainability practices drive economic efficiency and cost savings.

Zalatar and Clark's (2019) composite sustainability index based on QBLR emphasizes the framework's practicality. This index allows manufacturing firms to measure sustainability across economic, social, environmental, and governance dimensions, promoting transparency and accountability. The Nigerian study's findings align with this, showing that detailed disclosures in all four QBLR pillars lead to significant cost savings, proving QBLR is a practical strategy for enhancing cost efficiency and corporate sustainability.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings suggest that quadruple bottom line reporting, which encompasses economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures, significantly enhances cost-saving among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Quadruple bottom line reporting compels manufacturing firms to be more transparent and accountable in their operations. Economic disclosures require them to meticulously assess their financial performance, social disclosures entail examining their social impact, environmental disclosures demand tracking environmental footprints, and governance disclosures necessitate assessing internal controls and ethical practices. This heightened accountability can lead to a more thorough evaluation of operational efficiency and cost-saving opportunities.

The focus on environmental disclosures within quadruple bottom line reporting often encourages companies to identify and eliminate inefficiencies in their manufacturing processes. By reducing resource consumption and waste, companies can realize significant cost savings. Governance disclosures, a part of quadruple bottom line reporting, often require firms to assess and mitigate various risks, including regulatory, reputational, and operational risks. By identifying these risks and taking measures to reduce or eliminate them, companies can potentially save significant costs that might have been incurred due to non-compliance or unforeseen incidents.

Manufacturing firms that engage in comprehensive sustainability reporting often attract investors who are not just focused on financial returns but also care about a company's environmental and social impact. This can translate into improved access to capital and more favorable financing terms, ultimately reducing the cost of capital for these firms. Companies that are proactive in reporting on their social and environmental

initiatives may gain a competitive edge. This can lead to increased market share, higher sales, and better pricing power, which ultimately contribute to cost-saving through higher revenue and more efficient operations. Social disclosures within quadruple bottom line reporting can help manufacturing firms build stronger relationships with customers who prioritize products and services from socially responsible companies. Similarly, supply chain partners may prefer to work with firms that adhere to environmental and ethical standards, potentially reducing procurement costs and increasing reliability.

By implication, disclosing and adhering to governance standards can help manufacturing firms avoid costly regulatory fines and legal issues. Non-compliance often leads to substantial financial penalties and can disrupt operations. Quadruple bottom line reporting can help companies preemptively address governance issues, thereby preventing these costly consequences. In the context of Nigeria, where sustainability concerns are becoming increasingly important due to environmental challenges, social disparities, and evolving governance standards, the adoption of quadruple bottom line reporting can offer manufacturing firms a strategic advantage (El Daly, 2020). It aligns with global trends in sustainable business practices and can position these firms to enjoy cost-saving opportunities. Moreover, it aligns with growing investor and consumer demands for socially and environmentally responsible business practices, making it a sound strategy for long-term sustainability and financial success in the manufacturing sector.

Based on the conclusion above, the following three recommendations were made:

Comprehensive Adoption of Quadruple Bottom Line Reporting: To maximize the benefits of quadruple bottom line reporting, manufacturing firms should make a concerted effort to integrate economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures into their business practices in order to enhance transparency and accountability, leading to improved cost-saving opportunities. This comprehensive approach should become an integral part of the firm's corporate culture, rather than a mere reporting exercise.

Regular Performance Metrics and Benchmarking: Manufacturing firms should establish a system of regular performance metrics and benchmarking against industry standards and best practices. This involves setting specific, measurable, and time-bound goals related to economic, social, environmental, and governance performance. By tracking progress and comparing it to industry peers, companies can identify areas where they need improvement and opportunities for further cost-saving. Regular performance assessment will ensure that sustainability and cost-saving remain aligned and continually improved upon.

Stakeholder Engagement and Communication: Effective stakeholder engagement is crucial for the success of quadruple bottom line reporting. Manufacturing firms should actively engage with key stakeholders, including investors, customers, employees, suppliers, and local communities, to understand their expectations and concerns.

Contribution to Knowledge

Despite the growing emphasis on corporate sustainability, the focus of empirical research has largely been on the triple bottom line (TBL) reporting, which includes economic, social, and environmental dimensions. However, the concept of quadruple bottom line (QBL) reporting, which incorporates governance as a fourth dimension, remains underexplored in the literature, especially concerning its impact on cost savings in manufacturing firms. Prior studies, such as those by Manta, Tarulli, Morrone, and Toma (2020), have investigated the link between social disclosure and financial performance in banking institutions, emphasizing factors like gender diversity and equal opportunity policies. Similarly, Budsaratragoon and Jitmaneeoj (2019) analyzed the causal relationships among the four pillars of corporate sustainability, focusing on global companies, but did not specifically address the cost implications of these disclosures for manufacturing firms. Additionally, Zalatar and Clark (2019) introduced a composite sustainability index based on the QBL concept, but their work primarily concentrated on measuring sustainability performance rather than exploring the cost-saving benefits of QBL disclosures.

Given this backdrop, there is a noticeable gap in the literature regarding the specific impact of QBL disclosures on cost savings within the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. While existing studies by authors like Manta, Tarulli, Morrone, Toma, Budsaratragoon, Jitmaneeoj, Zalatar, and Clark have provided valuable insights into the broader implications of sustainability disclosures, they have not adequately addressed the potential cost savings that can arise from comprehensive QBL reporting. Furthermore, much of the existing research has focused on different sectors or regions, such as the banking industry in the European Union (Manta, Tarulli, Morrone, and Toma, 2020) or global companies in developed markets (Budsaratragoon and Jitmaneeoj, 2019), leaving a gap in understanding how QBL disclosures affect manufacturing firms in emerging economies like Nigeria. This study filled this gap by investigating how QBL disclosures—specifically economic, social, environmental, and governance disclosures—can lead to cost savings in Nigerian manufacturing firms, offering new insights that could inform both academic research and corporate practice.

Limitation of the Study and Suggestion for Further Studies

The sector scope was limited to manufacturing firms, which may not adequately represent the diverse impacts of such reporting across other industries. Secondly, the measure of cost saving was simplistic, using only the operating cost to total revenue ratio, which may not capture all dimensions of cost efficiency. Future studies should broaden the scope to include a variety of sectors and develop more comprehensive measures of cost savings to provide a broader perspectives of the implications of quadruple bottom line reporting.

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